

Anticancer studies of Z-His (Bzl)-OH (NSC169121) in Human cancer cells

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Abstract : Z-His (Bzl)-OH, was identified as potent cancer inhibitor from pharmacophore and virtual screening studies. The cytotoxicity of the Z-His (Bzl)-OH, quercetin and their combination were determined in two types of cancer cells, Human lung carcinoma cells (A549) and Human breast carcinoma cells and the cell viability was assessed using MTT assay and IC_{50} was determined. The IC_{50} of the Z-His (Bzl)-OH as 24.88 μ M, 24.8 μ M, quercetin as 18.6 μ M, 27.66 μ M and their combination as 6.72 μ M, 9.79 μ M in A549 and MCF-7 cell lines respectively. The combination of Z-His (Bzl)-OH and quercetin exhibited greater cytotoxic efficacy than did either Z-His (Bzl)-OH or quercetin alone. Quantitative real-time PCR was used to analyze the mRNA expression level of p53 and Bcl-2 in MCF-7 cells with Z-His (Bzl)-OH for 24 h. The RT-PCR results show that p53 gene expression increased while Bcl-2 gene expression decreased. The results showed that Z-His (Bzl)-OH exerted a dose-dependent inhibitory effect on the viability, via upregulation of p53 and downregulation of Bcl-2 gene.

Keywords : Apoptosis, Bcl-2, cytotoxicity, p53, quercetin, RT-PCR, Z-His (Bzl)-OH.

Introduction

Z-His (Bzl)-OH (NSC169121) ((S)-3-(1-benzyl-1H-imidazol-4-yl)-2-(((benzyloxy)carbonyl)amino)propanoic acid) was identified as potential inhibitor for cancer from previous pharmacophore and virtual screening studies of HDAC2 and virtual screening of ABCC1 transporter^{1,2}. Z-His (Bzl)-OH has histidine moiety, which plays an important role in the active centre of tumor specific catalase and experimental results show that the addition of histidine prevents apoptosis in tumor cells³. Quercetin (3,3',4',5,7-pentahydroxyflavone) is a flavonoid molecule and ubiquitous in nature. A number of actions make it as potential anticancer agent, including cell cycle regulation⁴. Number of studies have shown that flavonoids exhibit anticancer activity by inducing cell cycle arrest and apoptosis and inhibiting proliferation in different types of cancer cells in leukemia, breast cancer, ovarian cancer, lung cancer and colon cancer⁵. Apoptosis is a process of cell death to remove aberrant cells. In apoptosis most broadly studied genes are p53 and Bcl-2 family members which are major regulators of the apoptosis process and the caspases are major executioners⁶. Wild type p53 is a nuclear phosphoprotein that acts as a tumor suppressor and it induces several responses in cells, including dif-

ferentiation, senescence and DNA repair, cell cycle arrest and apoptotic cell death^{7,8}. These responses allow p53 to inhibit the growth of stressed cells either by cell cycle arrest or by removal of these cells from organism by apoptosis mechanism. Both responses prevent the replication of cells undergoing oncogenic changes so that it inhibits the tumor development^{9,10}. Earlier report indicates that p53 might lead to apoptosis indirectly by downregulating expression of Bcl-2¹¹. The Bcl-2 is a critical regulator of apoptosis and the overexpression of Bcl-2 has been associated with several malignancies. Bcl-2 is a prognostic marker in breast cancer¹². Bcl-2 family has fifteen members (e.g. anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 and Bcl-x_L) which suppress the apoptosis, while others (e.g. pro-apoptotic Bax, Bad, and Bak) enhance apoptosis¹³. Bcl-2 regulates both mitochondrial physiology and cell death and their deregulated expression often render cancer cells insensitive to apoptosis inducing anticancer activity¹⁴.

In the present study, the cytotoxicity of the Z-His (Bzl)-OH, quercetin and their combinations were analyzed against two types of Human cancer cell lines (A549 and MCF-7) and IC_{50} of the compounds was determined. The mRNA expression of p53 and Bcl-2 in MCF-7 cells

with Z-His (Bzl)-OH was analyzed in an attempt to understand the molecular action.

Results and discussion

Cell viability :

The cytotoxicity of Z-His (Bzl)-OH at the concentrations of 1, 10, 30, 50, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ was tested against Human lung carcinoma cells (A549) and Human breast carcinoma cells (MCF-7) and the cytotoxicity of quercetin. Further quercetin in combination with Z-His (Bzl)-OH at difference concentrations of 1, 10, 25, 50, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ was tested against A549 and MCF-7 using MTT assay for 24 h. The cytotoxic effect of Z-His (Bzl)-OH, quercetin and their combinations on A549 and MCF-7 cancer cell lines after 24 h of incubation were shown in Fig. 2. The cell viability percentage on A549 and MCF-7 cancer cells listed in Table 1. MTT results shows that when the concentration of Z-His (Bzl)-OH increased to 10, 30, 50, 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$ the cell viability was reduced to

Fig. 1. Chemical structure of Z-His (Bzl)-OH (NSC169121) and quercetin.

Fig. 2. % of cell viability of Z-His (Bzl)-OH in (a) Human lung carcinoma cells (A549), (b) Human breast carcinoma cells (MCF-7); and quercetin (Q), quercetin + Z-His (Bzl)-OH combination (Q+D) in (c) Human lung carcinoma cells (A549), (d) Human breast carcinoma cells (MCF-7) determined by MTT assay.

Table 1. Cell viability of the Z-His (Bzl)-OH, quercetin and their combination on Human lung carcinoma cells (A549) and Human breast carcinoma cells (MCF-7)

Compound name	Concentration	A549	MCF-7
Control	1	100	100
Z-His (Bzl)-OH	1	122.85	106.74
	10	87.14	77.91
	30	75	70.55
	50	57.85	53.98
	100	58.57	57.055
Quercetin	1	92.37288	91.44
	10	76.35593	83.2
	25	65.33898	72.4
	50	42.71186	65.36
	100	30.42373	43.52
Z-His (Bzl)-OH + Quercetin	1	80.33898	84.32
	10	66.18644	74.96
	25	54.91525	67.28
	50	43.47458	56.08
	100	26.52542	35.92

87.1%, 75%, 57.8% and 58.5% in A549 cancer cell line and to 77.9%, 70.5%, 53.9% and 57% in MCF-7 cancer cell lines respectively. IC₅₀ for the compound Z-His (Bzl)-OH is 94.42 µg/mL (24.88 µM) in A549 and 94.11 µg/mL (24.8 µM) in MCF-7 cancer cell lines. The IC₅₀ of the quercetin observed as 56.40 µg/mL (18.6 µM) in A549 and 83.61 µg/mL (27.66 µM) in MCF-7 cancer cell lines. When the concentration of the quercetin compound increases to 10, 25, 50 and 100 µg/mL the cell viability decreases to 76.3%, 65.3%, 42.7% and 30.4% in A549 cancer cell lines and 83.2%, 72.4%, 65.3% and 43.5% in MCF-7 cancer cell line. The combination of the quercetin and Z-His (Bzl)-OH compound tested against A549 and MCF-7 cancer cell lines shows better results compared to separate availability of Z-His (Bzl)-OH and quercetin. The IC₅₀ for the combination of compounds was observed as 45.8 µg/mL (6.72 µM) in A549 and 66.75 µg/mL (9.79 µM) in MCF-7 cancer cell lines. The combination of Z-His (Bzl)-OH and quercetin at 1 : 1 ratio for 24 h had a significant effect on A549 and MCF-7 cancer cell lines compared to their individual contributions of Z-His (Bzl)-OH and quercetin. In conclusion the enhanced activity of the inhibitor Z-His (Bzl)-OH is observed with the association of quercetin.

Z-His (Bzl)-OH – regulated gene expression :

In this study, quantitative real-time PCR was utilized to analyze the mRNA levels of apoptotic markers (p53, Bcl-2) in MCF-7 cells. The Bcl-2 family of proteins plays an important role in the regulation of apoptosis. Thus, in order to understand the molecular or biochemical mechanisms by which Z-His (Bzl)-OH induces apoptosis in MCF-7 cells, the expression levels of p53 and Bcl-2 after Z-His (Bzl)-OH treatment was analyzed. Upregulation of p53 and downregulation of Bcl-2 were observed after 24 h of treatment with Z-His (Bzl)-OH. The real time quantitative RT-PCR data demonstrated that treatment of MCF-7 cells with Z-His (Bzl)-OH shows decreased expression of Bcl-2 mRNA level in the presence of 94.11 µg/mL of compound after 24 h of treatment. Fig. 3 shows the expression data for treatment after 24 h, the anti-apoptotic gene Bcl-2 mRNA expression was downregulated by

Fig. 3. Effect of Z-His (Bzl)-OH on the mRNA expression levels of β-actin, p53 and Bcl-2 in MCF-7 cells after 24 h.

factor of 2.42 and the mRNA level of tumour suppression gene p53 was 0.93 fold increased after treatment with 94.11 µg/mL of compound in comparison with control (β-actin) (Table 2).

The mRNA expression levels were analyzed in p53

Table 2. mRNA expression of Z-His (Bzl)-OH on Bcl-2 and p53 in MCF-7 cells

	Bcl-2	p53
Control	1.1	0.934
Treated	-2.42	1.84

and Bcl-2 genes in response to compound exposure in MCF-7 cell lines because apoptosis controlled by these pathways. Quantitative real-time PCR results showed that Z-His (Bzl)-OH upregulated the mRNA level of cell cycle checkpoint protein p53 and expression of anti-apoptotic Bcl-2 was downregulated in cells exposed to Z-His (Bzl)-OH. The compound has shown increased expression of pro-apoptotic protein p53 and reduced anti-apoptotic protein Bcl-2. In the present study Z-His (Bzl)-OH simultaneously increases the expression of p53 and leads to decrease expression of Bcl-2 suggests their important role in apoptotic cell death by compound.

Experimental

Anticancer activity :

Z-His (Bzl)-OH (NSC169121) and quercetin compounds were purchased from the Sigma-Aldrich, whose chemical structures are shown in Fig. 1. Human lung carcinoma cells (A549) and Human breast carcinoma cells (MCF-7) were used for screening the anticancer activity of the Z-His (Bzl)-OH (NSC169121), quercetin and their combination using MTT (3-[4,5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl]-2,5-diphenyltetrazolium bromide) assay¹⁵. The compound was dissolved in 10% dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) to give a final concentration of DMSO not more than 0.5% and did not affect cell survival. The cells were plated separately in 96 well plates at a concentration of 1×10^5 cells/well. After 24 h, cells were washed twice with 100 μ L of serum-free medium and starved for an hour at 37 °C. After starvation, cells were treated with various concentrations of Z-His (Bzl)-OH compound (1, 10, 30, 50, 100 μ g/mL), quercetin (1, 10, 25, 50, 100 μ g/mL) and Z-His (Bzl)-OH and quercetin combination (1, 10, 25, 50, 100 μ g/mL) for 24 h. At the end of the treatment period the medium was aspirated and serum free medium containing MTT (0.5 mg/ml) was added and incubated for 4 h at 37 °C in a CO₂ incubator.

The MTT containing medium was then discarded and the cells were washed with PBS (200 μ L). The crystals were then dissolved by adding 100 μ L of DMSO and this was mixed thoroughly. The absorbance of the purple blue formazan dye was measured in a microplate reader at 570 nm using Biorad 680 spectrophotometer. The percentage of cell viability was calculated. The concentration of the compound causing 50% inhibition of cancer cell growth

was considered as IC₅₀.

RNA isolation and RT-PCR (Reverse transcription polymerase chain reaction) :

Total RNA was isolated from MCF-7 cell lines using TRIZOL (Sigma, India). The samples were incubated for 5 min at room temperature to permit complete dissociation of nucleoprotein complexes, 0.25-ml portions of chloroform were added, and the samples were centrifuged at 12,000 \times g for 15 min at 4 °C. Upper aqueous phase was mixed with five milligrams of RNase-free glycogen and 0.5 ml of isopropyl alcohol were introduced to precipitate nucleic acids for 15 min at room temperature and the pellets were washed with 75% ethanol (in DEPC-treated water). Pellets were resuspended in RNase free water, and DNase I treatment was performed. RT-PCR was performed in triplicate using SuperScript™ two step RT-PCR with platinum® Taq kit. For cDNA synthesis, complementary DNA was synthesized from 1 μ g total RNA from each sample in 20 μ L of reaction buffer (contained 50 mM Tris-HCl, pH 8.3, 75 mM KCl and 3 mM MgCl₂) using SuperScript II reverse transcriptase enzyme (Genetech, RT-PCR mix) in a 20 μ L volume reaction containing 10 mM dithiothreitol, 10 U RNase inhibitor (Promega, Madison), 1 mM dNTPs and 2.5 μ M random hexamers. Each sample was incubated for 45 min at 45 °C, followed by 10 min at 72 °C in an Agilent amplicon system, the prepared cDNA was stored in -20 °C for further use. The cDNA (1 μ L) was then amplified in 20 μ L of reaction buffer for 40 cycles of denaturation (96 °C for 30 s), annealing (56 °C for 30 s) and extension (72 °C for 30 s) using primers^{16,17}.

Real-time RT-PCR was performed by monitoring the increase in fluorescence intensity of the SYBR Green dye with a Rotor-Gene 3000 real-time PCR apparatus (Corbett Research). All measurements were performed in triplicate.

Quantitative data analysis of real-time PCR :

Real-time RT-PCR data were represented as C_t values, where C_t was defined as the threshold cycle of PCR when amplified product was first detected¹⁸. The C_t or threshold value of the target sequence is directly proportional to the absolute concentration when compared with the threshold value for reference genes (β -actin). The relative expression level of target gene (Bcl-2) were plot-

ted as fold change compared to control and determined by the $2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t}$ relative quantification algorithm. The factor X by which the amount of the changed gene can be calculated with the formula :

$$X = 2^{-\Delta\Delta C_t \text{ sample}}$$

where $\Delta\Delta C_t = (C_t \text{ of target})_{\text{control}} - (C_t \text{ of target} \times \beta\text{-actin})_{\text{sample}}$.

Conclusion

In the present study, the cytotoxicity of the Z-His (Bzl)-OH, quercetin and their combination were determined in Human lung carcinoma cells (A549) and Human breast carcinoma cells (MCF-7) using MTT assay. The A549 and MCF-7 cells were exposed to different concentrations of Z-His (Bzl)-OH, quercetin and their combination for 24 h. The MTT result shows IC_{50} value of the Z-His (Bzl)-OH is 24.88 μM and 24.8 μM , for quercetin as 18.6 μM and 27.66 μM and their combination as 6.72 μM and 9.79 μM in A549 and MCF-7 cancer cell lines respectively. We demonstrated the enhanced activity of Z-His (Bzl)-OH in association of quercetin. Further quantitative real-time PCR analysis shows that mRNA levels involved in the apoptosis was altered by Z-His (Bzl)-OH. Overall the study suggests that Z-His (Bzl)-OH induce apoptosis in MCF-7 cells via p53 and Bcl-2 pathways.

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